

SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC IMPORTANCE OF TOURISM MANAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT

This scientific article studies the social and economic significance of tourism management. The current state of tourism in Uzbekistan and its role in the economy, as well as important aspects of sustainable development in the tourism sector, are analyzed. The article also presents proposals for improving tourism management, including recommendations for the modernization of tourism infrastructure, training qualified personnel, and the development of sustainable tourism.

In recent years, the tourism industry has become one of the fastest growing sectors globally. According to the World Tourism Organization (UNWTO), international travel worldwide is expected to increase by 20% to 285 million in 2024. This means that tourism's share of the economy has reached 9% [8]. However, this growth has also been accompanied by problems such as "overtourism" (excessive tourist arrivals).

Uzbekistan's tourism is also showing significant growth. In 2023, more than 7 million foreign tourists visited the country, which is 26.9% more than 5.2 million in 2022. In terms of travel purposes, 5.6 million people visited to visit relatives, more than 773 thousand for recreation, and more than 143 thousand for work-related purposes. In addition, more than 61 thousand foreign patients chose to receive treatment in Uzbekistan [7].

As a result of reforms in the tourism sector, 183 new hotels and 356 family guesthouses were launched in 2023, which led to the creation of more than 70,000 new jobs. 508 investment projects were also implemented, and 5 villages were granted the status of "Tourist Village".

This article aims to scientifically analyze the economic and social significance of tourism management, to show its role and opportunities in society. In particular, the prospects and existing problems of this sector are analyzed using the example of Uzbekistan. During the study, conclusions are drawn based on available statistical data, international experience and practical examples.

Tourism management is a complex management system that includes the processes of organizing, managing, planning and controlling tourism activities. Its main task is to meet the needs of tourists, improve the quality of services and ensure the efficiency of the industry. In the experience of developed countries, tourism management has been formed as a separate science and field of practice, and special specialists are trained in this area.

The main areas of tourism management include: service marketing, financial management, strategic planning, human resource management, logistics, customer service and the implementation of digital technologies. Each department complements each other and

contributes to the success of the overall result. Especially in modern competitive conditions, it is important to correctly understand customer needs and develop appropriate offers.

Modern tourism management is based on the principles of sustainability. According to this principle, tourism activities should be aimed not only at generating economic profit, but also at environmental protection, preserving cultural heritage and taking into account the interests of local populations. Therefore, today many countries are paying great attention to the development of ecotourism, cultural tourism and experiential tourism.

In addition, the rapid development of digital technologies has led to a new level of tourism management. With the help of online booking systems, artificial intelligence-based services, virtual guides and analytical platforms, tourists' needs are being studied in more depth and customized services are being offered. This helps to increase efficiency in the tourism sector and strengthen customer trust.

Although tourism management in Uzbekistan is not yet fully developed, positive changes have been observed in this regard in recent years. In particular, cooperation between the Tourism Committee, the "Uzbekistan.travel" platform, tourism universities and the private sector is gradually being systematized. In particular, increased competition among local tour operators is leading to an increase in the quality of service and the level of management.

Table 1.

Economic impact of the tourism industry: key indicators

Indicator	Uzbekistan (2023)	Global (2022)	Notes
Tourism's share in GDP	5,10%	10%	Tourism's contribution to Uzbekistan's GDP.
Number of foreign tourists	7 million +	1,5 billion+	Uzbekistan and the size of the global tourism market.
Tourism export	\$1.2 billion	\$1.6 trillion	Foreign exchange earnings from tourism.
New jobs	70,000+	319 million (global)	New jobs created by the tourism sector.
Investments	508 projects	-	Tourism investments made in Uzbekistan.
Number of hotels	183 new hotels	-	Opening of new hotels in Uzbekistan.

Source: Author's work

This table presents some key indicators of the economic impact of the tourism sector, compared on a national and global scale. The table provides a clearer picture of the contribution of tourism to the economy..

Tourism has a great social value, contributing to the preservation of culture and heritage, increasing mutual understanding and respect between societies, and creating new opportunities for local populations. Through tourism, cultural exchange between people increases, which strengthens peace and stability on a global scale. Cultural and historical monuments are visited by travelers, and attention to their preservation increases. For example, cities in Uzbekistan such as Samarkand, Bukhara and Khiva, with the development of tourism, contribute not only to economic growth, but also to the preservation of cultural sites. At the same time, tourism creates new jobs and business opportunities for local residents. By working with tourists, local residents acquire new skills. This increases social equality in society, especially for people living in rural and remote areas. The development of tourism provides new opportunities for many social strata, which makes society more just and equal.

Through the tourism sector, mutual understanding and intercultural cooperation develop between people, which leads to social stability on a global scale.

Tourism also contributes significantly to education and skills development. Education and training are available for professionals working in the tourism sector, which not only makes workers in this sector more qualified, but also contributes to social and economic growth in other sectors. Travel helps to reduce cultural and social differences between people, and by getting to know different nations and cultures, people can develop mutual respect and understanding.

The development of the tourism sector, while creating many opportunities, also creates a number of problems related to tourism management. Effective strategies and innovative approaches are needed to solve these problems. One of the main problems of tourism management is the insufficient quality of infrastructure and services. For example, in some regions, hotel and transport systems are poorly developed, which creates inconvenience for tourists. There are also difficulties in creating competitive tourism products. Many countries are still unable to provide innovative and attractive offers for the international tourism market.

In addition, the impact of tourism on the environment is also a pressing problem. The increased demand from tourists for open natural and cultural sites can lead to their degradation. For example, pollution and depletion of natural resources are common in popular tourist destinations. Therefore, it is necessary to develop measures to ensure the sustainable development of tourism and environmental safety.

In addition, the lack of qualified human resources in the tourism sector also poses major problems. The lack of sufficient qualifications of workers in hotels, restaurants and transport systems is an obstacle to providing quality services to tourists. For effective tourism management, it is necessary to train qualified specialists and improve the education system[6].

Government policies also play an important role in tourism development. Effective government policies are needed to develop tourism infrastructure and support sustainable tourism. For example, tax incentives, subsidies, and investment programs can attract significant amounts of money to the tourism sector. Improving marketing and branding strategies can also help increase the competitiveness of the tourism sector.

There are several development paths to address the problems. The most important of these is the development of sustainable tourism, that is, reducing the environmental and social impact of tourism. This, in turn, includes the use of innovative technologies in the tourism sector, the development of environmentally friendly transport systems, and the preservation of cultural heritage. However, effective cooperation between the state and the private sector is necessary for this process to be implemented. It is also important to create a system based on mutual benefits between local residents and tourists.

The development of tourism management also requires the adoption of innovative technologies. For example, digital platforms, mobile applications and artificial intelligence can be used to create new services for travelers. In addition, the development of "smart" tourism technologies can provide more convenient and efficient services for tourists.

Tourism management plays an important role in the economic and social development of countries. Economically, the tourism sector is of great importance in generating export revenues, providing new jobs, and developing international cooperation. The tourism potential of Uzbekistan, with its historical and cultural wealth and natural resources, is of great interest not only to the domestic but also to the international market. However, there is still a need to improve the infrastructure and quality of services in the tourism sector[5].

From a social point of view, tourism promotes cultural exchange, strengthens mutual understanding between societies and creates new opportunities for local residents. Also, ensuring the sustainable development and environmental safety of tourism is one of the

important issues. Situations such as the depletion of natural resources and the degradation of cultural sites create the need to introduce eco-tourism and sustainable management.

A number of measures should be taken to improve tourism management. First of all, it is necessary to pay special attention to the development of sustainable tourism. Sustainable tourism should ensure economic and social benefits without harming the environment. This, in turn, means the introduction of environmentally friendly technologies, the development of "green" tourism and the preservation of natural resources.

- It is necessary to modernize the tourism infrastructure. It is important to improve the quality of hotel services, transport systems and other infrastructure facilities, and create comfortable and safe conditions for tourists. The development of digital technologies, including mobile applications, online booking systems and "smart" tourism platforms, can increase convenience for travelers.

- It is also necessary to improve the education and training system. Training qualified personnel in the field of tourism management, organizing their continuous training and advanced training courses will increase the efficiency of the sector.

- Improving state policy and legal conditions also play an important role in the development of tourism. It is necessary to attract additional funds to the tourism sector through tax incentives, subsidies and investment programs, and strengthen cooperation between the private and public sectors.

- By improving marketing and branding strategies, it is possible to promote Uzbekistan's tourism potential on a global scale and attract new markets. It is necessary to develop competitive products in the tourism sector, offer new services for travelers, and make the country attractive in the tourism market.

In conclusion, by implementing the above proposals, it is possible to further increase the social and economic importance of the tourism sector, strengthen the country's position in the global tourism market. Ensuring sustainable development of tourism, establishing effective cooperation between the public and private sectors, and using innovative technologies can achieve further development of the sector.

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